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Effects Of Cooperative Learning Instructional Strategy And Lecture Method On Students' Achievement, Retention, And Attitude Towards Biology In Delta South Senatorial District

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ABSTRACT

This study examined the effects of cooperative learning instructional strategy and lecture method on students' achievement, retention, and attitude towards Biology. Four research questions and corresponding hypotheses guided the study. The study employed the pretest-posttest delayed-posttest planned variation quasi-experimental design. The population for the study consisted of 19,400 SS II biology students, consisting of 11,319 males and 8,081 females in Delta South Senatorial District. The sample size for the study comprised three hundred and six (306) SS II Biology students from six (6) intact classes of six (6) mixed secondary schools. Data were collected using validated instruments, the Biology Achievement Test (BAT), and the Students' Attitude towards Biology Questionnaire (SABQ), with a reliability coefficient of 0.79 and 0.78 established using Kuder-Richardson 21 formula and the Cronbach-alpha statistics, respectively. Data collected were analyzed using mean, standard deviation, independent sample t-test, and Analysis of Covariance. The study found that: there is a significant difference in the post-test mean achievement scores of students taught biology using cooperative learning instructional strategy and those taught using the lecture method, in favour of students taught using cooperative learning instructional strategy, there is no significant difference in the mean achievement scores of male and female students taught biology using co-operative learning instructional strategy, there is a significant difference in the retention scores of students taught biology using cooperative learning instructional strategy and those taught using the lecture method in favour of students using cooperative learning instructional strategy, and there is a significant difference in the mean attitude scores of students taught biology using cooperative learning instructional strategy and those taught using the lecture method in favour of students taught using cooperative learning instructional strategy. It was therefore recommended among others that biology teachers should adopt cooperative learning strategy in their classroom instruction as it actively engages students in collaborative learning, leading to improved understanding and long-term retention of concepts, and is equally effective for both genders.

Keywords: cooperative learning, lecture, instructional strategy, students, achievement, retention, attitude, biology.

INTRODUCTION

Biology is one of the science subjects that students must pass so as to qualify them to offer some science courses at the tertiary level of education. The knowledge of Biology provides students with opportunities to develop an understanding of the world we live in (Ekinfe, Olofinniyi, Fashikun, 2012). It is a basic science that deals with the study of living things and their diversity, as well as their interaction with one another and with their environment (Dan-Ogel & Shitu, 2012). Biology is an essential science subject because it provides learners with a fundamental understanding of life processes, living organisms, and the

interactions between humans and their environment, which are critical for personal health, environmental sustainability, agriculture, and national development. It equips students with the scientific literacy needed to make informed decisions about issues such as disease prevention, nutrition, biotechnology, and conservation. Moreover, Biology forms the foundation for many professional careers, including medicine, pharmacy, nursing, environmental science, and biotechnology. However, the abstract nature of many biological concepts and the wide range of topics it covers make effective teaching challenging when traditional lecture methods are used alone. Consequently, the teaching of Biology requires innovative instructional strategies that actively engage students, promote inquiry, and connect theory with real-life experiences. Such strategies and the use of models and simulations enhance students' understanding, stimulate curiosity, and improve retention and achievement by making learning more meaningful and learner-centered.

Nwagbo (2006) and Nwosu (2013), in their investigations, showed that biology instructors/teachers do not always use teaching methods that are efficient for biology teaching and learning. The instructional strategies they use do not bring about active engagement of students in the class and transfer of learning. For the teacher to function effectively in the present dynamic society, he/she must rise to the challenges of adopting effective teaching strategies in his/her classrooms. Teaching science in Nigerian secondary schools is dominated by the conventional lecture (teacher-centered) method. This method does not always produce students who are committed to science and who can reason critically and analytically (Salihu, 2015). This method has not been known to improve students' achievement significantly. The lecture method, which is mostly used in schools, can be said to be the simplest method for teachers because it does not require any strenuous arrangements. However, the lecture method is a teacher or content/subject-centred method of teaching. This makes the teacher a reservoir of knowledge, dispensing knowledge to students, who contribute very little or nothing to the instructional process, thereby making the students passive listeners as opposed to being active participants in terms of teacher-student interaction, student-student interaction, and student-interaction with learning materials. This methodology also encourages memorization and rote learning by students. Over the years, there has been a shift from memorization and rote learning to an all-embracing learning situation where learners are not passive but active. The lecture method is against the principle of learning by doing, and it does not take into consideration individual differences. Consequently, different scholars have developed innovative teaching strategies or methods that are learner-centred, to make students active in the teaching-learning process, with the tendency of improving students' ability to remember information for a longer period of time. One of such teaching strategies is cooperative learning.

Cooperative learning instructional strategy involves the teachers organizing students into small groups, which then work together to help one another learn academic content (Slavin, 2011). Cooperative learning consists of five basic elements: positive interdependence, promotive interaction, individual accountability, teaching of interpersonal and social skills, and quality of group processing. Learning situations are not cooperative if students are arranged into groups without positive interdependence (Johnson & Johnson, 2009). Positive interdependence means that in cooperative learning situations, students are required to work together as a cohesive group to achieve shared learning objectives (Yager, 2000). In the process, students must be responsible for their own learning and for the success of other group members' learning (Slavin, 2011). In other words, students must ensure that other members in their group complete the tasks and achieve the academic outcomes. The lesson will not be cooperative if students do not "*swim together*" in the group learning activities (Johnson, Johnson & Smith 2013). Hence, positive interdependence needs to be constructed in cooperative learning groups to help students work and learn together. Positive interdependence results in reciprocal interaction among individuals, which promotes each group member's productivity and achievement. Promotive interaction occurs as individuals encourage and facilitate each other's efforts to accomplish the group's goals. In cooperative learning groups, students are required to interact verbally with one another on learning tasks (Johnson & Johnson, 2009). As part of the cooperative learning condition, students are required to interact verbally with one another on learning tasks, exchange opinions, explain things, teach others, and present their understanding (Johnson, 2009).

Individual responsibility means that students ask for assistance, do their best work, present their ideas, learn as much as possible, take their tasks seriously, help the group operate well, and take care of one another. Positive interdependence is recognized to create “*responsibility forces*” that increase the individual accountability of group members for accomplishing shared work and facilitating other group members’ work. If there is no individual accountability, one or two group members may do all the work while others do nothing. If the achievement of the group depends on the individual learning of each group member, then group members are motivated to ensure that all group members master the material being studied. When group accountability and individual accountability exist in the group, the responsibility forces increase (Johnson & Johnson, 2009). In reality, students cannot work effectively if socially unskilled students are arranged into one group. If basic learning skills on cooperative interaction are not taught, group members cannot work together effectively to finish their tasks.

For teaching of Biology to be effectively and efficiently carried out, Biology teachers must shift from the predominant method of teaching to the constructivist learning strategies, where the learning is not centred on the teacher but on the students, using their existing knowledge to solve the problems presented to them by the teachers, for students’ academic achievements to be improved. Olanipekun and Aina (2014) see achievement as an observable or measurable behavior of a person or an animal in a particular situation, usually an experimental situation. This, therefore, means that achievement measures the behavior or an aspect of a feat that can be observed at a specific time. Students’ achievement is very important because it is a major criterion by which the effectiveness and success of any educational institution can be assessed.

Academic achievement is basically the product of the extent to which educational or instructional goals and objectives have been attained. Academic achievement is the performance outcomes that depict the extent to which a learner has accomplished specific goals that were the focus of activities in instructional environments such as educational institutions. Nwanze (2016) defined academic achievement as an outcome of learning, which expresses the extent to which instructional objectives have been met. Similarly, academic achievement can also be said to be students’ achievement in a school subject as designated by a score or mark obtained in a standard test. Ajaja (2013) found that cooperative strategy has a significant effect on Biology students’ achievement. Students’ achievement and retention are closely related, as higher academic achievement often reflects effective understanding, which enhances the ability to retain learned concepts over time, while strong retention supports sustained achievement in subsequent learning and assessments.

Retention is the ability of students to remember or recognize the content that has been taught and learned, which is very critical in teaching and learning. There are different ways in which one can easily retain knowledge. Ezeudu (2017) opined that active learning increases engagement and leads to much better retention. Many people seem to be confused and worried as to what factors are actually responsible for the poor academic retention in schools. This led many researchers to attribute poor retention ability to poor teaching techniques. To support this assertion, Salau (2009) submitted that many researchers have adduced that poor performance in public examinations is traceable to teaching techniques by teachers. The resultant effect is the low academic outcome in both internal and external examinations. Retention, therefore, means the ability to keep or retain the knowledge of what is learnt and be able to recall it when it is required. In the context of this study, retention is the ability to recall or remember what has been taught after a given time as a measure of students’ progress. When students retain what they have learnt, they attain good academic standing. This could spur students to develop a positive attitude toward the subject. Any teaching method that enables students to retain more knowledge is regarded as an effective method and should be recommended. This method could be capable of improving students’ attitudes towards biology.

Attitude is the tendency to think, feel, or act positively or negatively towards objects in our environment. Attitude is learned from society; affected by group norms, positive or negative attitude with reference to the object, and the strength of the effect is correlated to the content of the associated cognitive structure, determining the behavior, affect perception, education, and teacher education bring the change in attitude (Ahmed & Shaista, 2016). Attitude could be defined as a learner’s predisposition to respond positively or negatively to a specific object, situation, or person. Attitude can also be seen as a mental or neural

readiness, organized through experience, exerting a directive and dynamic influence upon an individual's response to all objects or situations with which it is related. The concept of attitude is the total of a person's inclinations and feelings, prejudices or bias, preconceived notions, ideas, threats, and convictions about any specific topic. Owen (2008) asserted that the declining student attitude in science courses and careers is a worldwide concern that has prompted science education reform efforts on an international scale. Recently, students' attitudes have been described as a critical factor that affects the quality of teaching and learning. Ksheerasagar and Kavyakishore (2013) pointed out that attitudes are developed, not inborn. They also added that one of the chief objectives of education is the development of desirable attitudes in the students. This agrees with George (2006), who reported that one of the key factors in learning science is attitude, and the development of positive attitudes towards science can motivate students' interest in science education. It is therefore obvious that the teacher must understand the various dimensions of an attitude and also develop a positive attitude in the student, like an attitude toward studies, self, colleagues, and certain ideals. It therefore follows that student attitude can be modified by the use of appropriate instructional strategies. Biology students' attitudes toward the subject may vary by gender, as differences in socialization, learning experiences, and classroom interactions can influence how male and female students perceive, engage with, and develop interest in biology.

Gender in this study refers to the state of being male or female. It is the characteristics by means of which people define male or female. It is one of the factors that have been empirically reported to influence students' achievement in science subjects. While some studies have proven that male students performed significantly better than their female counterparts in Mathematics (Effiom & Abdullahi, 2021), others have shown that female students performed better than their male counterparts in Physics (Ademola & Nadaraj, 2018). However, studies have equally revealed no significant difference in the mean achievement and retention scores of male and female students in Basic Science (Umar, Ossom & Egbita, 2021). Furthermore, it is observed that boys appear to show a more positive attitude to science and technology subjects, while girls show a negative attitude. With this, it becomes necessary to look for a method that will have equal influence on male and female students' attitudes.

Since the co-operative learning instructional strategy and the lecture method differ in their principles of presentation of content to be learnt, it becomes necessary to find out if there will be differences in students' achievement, retention, and attitude towards Biology when taught with the lecture method and cooperative instructional strategy. It is against this background, therefore, that this study sought to compare the effects of co-operative learning and lecture methods on students' achievements, retention, and attitude towards Biology in Delta South Senatorial District, and also determine whether they are gender dependent, to isolate and recommend the most effective method of the two.

Statement of the Problem

In recent times, observations on students' academic achievement in science and particularly in biology in the result of Senior Secondary School Certificate Examination (SSCE), conducted by West African Examination Council (WAEC) and National Examination Council (NECO) indicate that very few students perform well in Biology examination. The outcry for poor performance in the West African Senior School Certificate Examination (WASSCE), especially in the science subjects and particularly in Biology, is notable in many states in Nigeria, including Delta State. The West African Examination Council's Chief Examiners' Report for May-June examinations from 2019 – 2024 lends credence to this poor performance/achievement of students in Biology. According to the reports, the weaknesses of students in WAEC examinations include: inability to interpret questions; poor command of English language; poor drawing; inability to link structural features with their functions; poor knowledge application of some biological concepts; shallow knowledge of subject matter; inability to report experiment at sequential manner; construction of 'food chain' without showing direction with arrow and poor response to ecology questions. The abysmal achievements as a result of these weaknesses have been attributed to the teaching method used in the teaching of Biology, among other factors. Teachers at the secondary school level were held responsible for the growing decline in students' academic achievement since the quality of education depends on the teachers, as reflected in the performance of their duties. The results of learning are always influenced by the nature and quality of the methods and techniques

employed for the teaching and learning of a particular content, subject matter, or learning experience. Since the lecture and cooperative methods have different characteristics, it became necessary to determine their effects on students' achievement, retention, and attitude towards biology. The statement of the problem, therefore, is: Will the use of the cooperative learning instructional strategy improve students' achievement, retention, and attitude towards biology more than the lecture method?

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What is the difference in the mean achievement scores of students taught Biology using cooperative learning instructional strategy and those taught using the lecture method?
2. What is the difference in the mean achievement scores of male and female students taught Biology using cooperative learning instructional strategy and lecture method?
3. What is the difference in the retention scores of students taught Biology using cooperative learning instructional strategy and those taught using the lecture method?
4. What is the difference in the mean attitude scores of students taught Biology using cooperative learning instructional strategy and those taught using the lecture method?

Hypotheses

The following corresponding hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance.

1. There is no significant difference in the mean achievement scores of students taught Biology using cooperative learning instructional strategy and those taught using the lecture method.
2. There is no significant difference in the mean achievement scores of male and female students taught Biology using cooperative learning instructional strategy lecture method.
3. There is no significant difference in the retention scores of students taught Biology using cooperative learning instructional strategy and those taught using the lecture method.
4. There is no significant difference in the mean attitude scores of students taught Biology using cooperative learning instructional strategy and those taught using the lecture method.

METHODOLOGY

The study adopted the pretest, posttest, delayed posttest, planned variation quasi-experimental design. The population of the study comprised of all public senior secondary school two (SSII) Biology students in Delta South Senatorial District of Delta State. There are 133 public secondary schools in Delta South Senatorial District with a population of 19,400 SS II Biology students consisting of 11,319 males and 8,081 females. The sample size for the study comprised three hundred and six (306) SS II Biology students from six (6) intact classes of six (6) mixed secondary schools. The instruments used for data collection, which were duly face and content validated, are the Biology Achievement Test (BAT), and the Students' Attitude towards Biology Questionnaire (SABQ), with reliability coefficients of 0.79 and 0.78, respectively, determined using Kuder-Richardson Formula – 21 (K-R-21) and Cronbach-alpha. Before the commencement of the treatment, the six (6) schools randomly selected for the study were randomly assigned into groups: the cooperative learning instructional strategy (CLIS) group and the lecture method (LM) group. The groups were pre-tested to establish equivalence and to ensure that any observed changes at post-test could be attributed to the treatment administered. Following the pre-test, the groups underwent the treatment, where one group was taught using cooperative learning instructional strategy and the lecture method. Post-tests were then conducted immediately after the treatment. Thereafter, a delayed posttest was conducted four weeks after the posttest. Data collected were analyzed with mean, standard deviation for the research questions, while the hypotheses were tested at a 0.05 level of significance using t-test, and Analysis of Variance (ANOVA).

RESULTS

Research Question 1: *What is the difference in the mean achievement scores of students taught Biology using cooperative learning instructional strategy and those taught using the lecture method?*

Table 1:

Descriptive statistics of mean and standard deviation comparison of the pretest and posttest mean achievement scores of students taught biology using cooperative learning instructional strategy, and lecture method

GROUPS	N	PRETEST			POSTEST		
		\bar{X}	\bar{X} Diff	SD	\bar{X}	\bar{X} Diff	SD
CLIS	156	16.47	1.39	2.31	41.15	9.31	5.47
LM	150	17.87		3.64	31.84		3.80

Table 1 shows that at pretest, the group exposed to cooperative learning instructional strategy had a mean score of 16.47 with a standard deviation of 2.31, while the group exposed to the lecture method had a mean score of 17.87 with a standard deviation of 3.64. The difference between the two groups is 1.39. This indicates a difference between the groups at pre-test. At post-test, the group exposed to cooperative learning instructional strategy had a mean achievement score of 41.15 with a standard deviation of 5.47, while the group exposed to the lecture method had a mean achievement score of 31.84 with a standard deviation of 3.80. The difference is 9.31. This indicates a difference between the groups. To determine if the difference was significant, Hypothesis 1 was tested.

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant difference in the mean achievement scores of students taught Biology using cooperative learning instructional strategy and those taught using the lecture method.

Table 2:

Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) conducted to determine the mean achievement scores of students taught Biology using cooperative learning instructional strategy and those taught using the lecture method

Dependent Variable: Posttest

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Corrected Model	9339.318 ^a	2	4669.659	345.875	.000
Intercept	3578.101	1	3578.101	265.025	.000
Pretest	2705.668	1	2705.668	200.405	.000
Group	8284.458	1	8284.458	613.619	.000
Error	4090.800	303	13.501		
Total	423072.000	306			
Corrected Total	13430.118	305			

a. R Squared = .695 (Adjusted R Squared = .693)

Table 2 shows that the calculated F-value for teaching methods is 613.619, and its p-value is 0.000. Since the p-value of 0.000 is less than the 0.05 level of significance, **F (1, 303) = 613.619, p = 0.000**. The null hypothesis, which states that there is no significant difference in the mean achievement scores of students taught biology using cooperative learning instructional strategy and those taught using the lecture method, is rejected. Therefore, there is a statistically significant difference in the posttest mean achievement scores of students taught with the two methods, after adjusting for pretest scores.

Research Question 2: *What is the difference in the mean achievement scores of male and female students taught Biology using cooperative learning instructional strategy and lecture method?*

Table 3: Descriptive statistics of mean and standard deviation comparison of the post-test mean achievement scores of male and female students taught biology using cooperative learning instructional strategy and lecture method

Groups	Sex	N	\bar{X}	\bar{X} Diff.	SD
CLIS	Male	83	41.73	1.24	5.31
	Female	73	40.49		5.61
LM	Male	77	31.69	0.31	3.50
	Female	73	32.00		4.12

Table 3 shows a posttest mean achievement score of 41.73 with a standard deviation of 5.31 for male students taught Biology using cooperative learning instructional strategy, while their female counterparts had a posttest mean achievement score of 40.49 with a standard deviation of 5.61. The mean difference between both sexes is 1.24, in favour of the male students. For those taught with lecture method, the Table shows a posttest mean achievement score of 31.69 with a standard deviation of 3.50 for male students, while their female counterparts had a posttest mean achievement score of 32.00 with a standard deviation of 4.12. The mean difference between both sexes is 0.31, in favour of the female students.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant difference in the mean achievement scores of male and female students taught biology using cooperative learning instructional strategy and lecture method.

Table 4: Independent Samples t-test Comparison of Posttest Achievement Scores of Male and Female Students taught Biology using Cooperative Learning Instructional Strategy

Groups	Sex	N	\bar{X}	SD	df	t-cal	Sig. (2-tailed)	Decision
CLIS	Male	83	41.73	5.31	154	1.42	0.158	H₀₃ is not rejected
	Female	73	40.49	5.61				
LM	Male	77	31.69	3.50	148	0.500	0.552	H₀₃ is not rejected
	Female	73	32.00	4.12				

Table 4 shows that there is no significant difference in the post-test mean achievement scores of male and female students taught biology using cooperative learning instructional strategy and lecture method. This is because, for cooperative learning instructional strategy, the calculated significant value of 0.158 is greater than the critical significant value of 0.05, while for the lecture method, the calculated significant value of 0.552 is greater than the critical Significant value of 0.05. With this, Ho₂, which states that there was no significant difference in the mean achievement scores of male and female students taught biology using cooperative learning instructional strategy and lecture method, is not rejected.

Research Question 3: *What is the difference in the retention scores of students taught biology using cooperative learning instructional strategy and those taught using the lecture method?*

Table 5: Descriptive statistics of mean and standard deviation comparison of the delayed posttest (retention) scores of biology students taught using cooperative learning instructional strategy, and lecture method

Groups	N	\bar{X} (Retention)	\bar{X} Diff.	SD
CLIS	156	37.71	9.39	3.80
LM	150	28.32		3.90

Table 5 shows that students taught biology using cooperative learning instructional strategy had a mean delayed posttest score (retention) of 37.71, with a standard deviation of 3.80, while those taught using lecture method had a mean delayed posttest score of 28.32, which indicates the retention score with a standard deviation of 3.90. The mean difference is 9.39. This suggests that there is a difference between the delayed posttest scores (Retention) of the groups. To determine if this difference is significant, Hypothesis 3 was tested. The result is shown in Table 6.

Hypothesis 3: There is no significant difference in the retention scores of students taught biology using cooperative learning instructional strategy and those taught using the lecture method.

Table 6:

Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) conducted to determine the difference in the retention scores of students taught biology using cooperative learning instructional strategy and those taught using the lecture method

Dependent Variable: Dposttest

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Corrected Model	13154.032 ^a	2	6577.016	3980.719	.000
Intercept	30.244	1	30.244	18.305	.000
Posttest	6418.454	1	6418.454	3884.750	.000
Group	4.317	1	4.317	2.613	.017
Error	500.622	303	1.652		
Total	349004.000	306			
Corrected Total	13654.654	305			

a. R Squared = .963 (Adjusted R Squared = .963)

Table 6 shows that the calculated F-value for teaching methods is 2.613, and its p-value is 0.017. Since the p-value of 0.000 is less than the 0.05 level of significance, $F(1, 303) = 2.613$, $p = 0.017$. The null hypothesis, which states that there is no significant difference in the retention scores of students taught biology using cooperative learning instructional strategy and those taught using the lecture method, is rejected. Therefore, there is a statistically significant difference in the retention scores of students taught biology using cooperative learning instructional strategy and those taught using the lecture method in favour of those taught using cooperative learning instructional strategy.

Research Question 4: *What is the difference in the mean attitude scores of students taught biology using cooperative learning instructional strategy and those taught using the lecture method.*

Table 7:

Descriptive statistics of mean and standard deviation comparison of the post-attitude test scores of students taught biology using co-operative learning instructional strategy, and lecture method

GROUPS	N	\bar{X}	\bar{X} Diff	SD
CLIS	156	58.72	3.19	4.23
LM	150	55.53		4.33

Table 7 shows that at posttest, the group exposed to CLIS had a post-attitude test score of 58.72 with a standard deviation of 4.23, while the group exposed to the lecture method had a post-attitude test score of 55.53 with a standard deviation of 4.33. The difference is 3.19. This indicates a difference between the groups.

Hypothesis 4: There is no significant difference in the mean attitude scores of students taught Biology using cooperative learning instructional strategy and those taught using the lecture method.

Table 8: Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) conducted to determine the difference in the attitude scores of students taught biology using cooperative learning instructional strategy and those taught using the lecture method

Dependent Variable: Post-Attitude-Test

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Corrected Model	3988.372 ^a	2	1994.186	257.256	.000
Intercept	2530.203	1	2530.203	326.404	.000
PreAttiTest	3209.699	1	3209.699	414.061	.000
Group	615.952	1	615.952	79.460	.000
Error	2348.782	303	7.752		
Total	1006125.000	306			
Corrected Total	6337.154	305			

a. R Squared = .629 (Adjusted R Squared = .627)

Table 8 shows that the calculated F-value for teaching methods is 79.460, and its p-value is 0.000. Since the p-value of 0.000 is less than the 0.05 level of significance, $F(1, 303) = 79.460$, $p = 0.000$. The null hypothesis, which states that there is no significant difference in the mean attitude scores of students taught Biology using cooperative learning instructional strategy and those taught using the lecture method, is rejected. Therefore, there is a statistically significant difference in the mean attitude scores of students taught Biology using cooperative learning instructional strategy and those taught using the lecture method in favour of those taught using cooperative learning instructional strategy. **Discussion**

The first finding of the study from Tables 1 and 2 showed a clear difference in the post-test achievement scores of students exposed to the cooperative learning instructional strategy and those taught using the lecture method. The mean difference of 9.31 points suggests a substantial advantage in favour of students taught with cooperative learning instructional strategy. This significant difference implies that the cooperative learning instructional strategy has a stronger and more positive effect on students' achievement in biology compared to the traditional lecture approach. The interactive nature of cooperative learning instructional strategy, which emphasizes student participation, group collaboration, peer explanation, shared responsibility, and active construction of knowledge, may have contributed to higher levels of engagement and deeper understanding of biology concepts. This aligns with social constructivist principles, which assert that learners achieve better outcomes when they interact, discuss, and co-construct knowledge within a learning community. This finding corroborate previous research that has reported the superiority of cooperative learning strategies over traditional teaching methods, such as findings of Kaymak, Kassymbek, Kalamkas, and Saydenov (2021), and Kingdom-Aaron, Etokeren, and Okwelle (2019).

The second finding of the study Table 2 and 3, indicated that both the cooperative learning instructional strategy and the lecture method enhanced students' achievement in biology, irrespective of gender. For the cooperative learning instructional strategy, both male and female students appear to have benefited equally from the collaborative, interactive, and group-oriented learning environment fostered by cooperative learning instructional strategy. The cooperative structure may have minimized gender-related performance differences by promoting equal participation, shared responsibilities, and peer support during learning activities. The absence of significant gender differences aligns with contemporary educational research, which indicates that when instructional strategies provide equal opportunities for engagement, communication, and hands-on participation, male and female students tend to perform at comparable levels. For the lecture method, the finding implies that the lecture method exerts a uniform effect on both male and female students, without giving any particular gender a performance advantage. Since the lecture method is predominantly teacher-centered and involves passive listening, note-taking, and limited student interaction, the learning experiences provided are largely the same for both genders. As a result, both male and female students appear to have obtained similar levels of understanding from the instructional process. These findings are consistent with those of Kingdom-Aaron, Etokeren, and

Okwelle (2019), Ahmad (2018), and Alhassan (2019), who found no significant difference between male and female students' achievement when exposed to biology content with cooperative learning instructional strategy and the lecture method.

The third finding of the study from Tables 5 and 6 showed that the cooperative learning instructional strategy significantly enhances students' retention of biology concepts better than the lecture method. The higher retention observed may be attributed to the active, student-centered nature of cooperative learning instructional strategy, where learners interact, discuss, explain ideas to peers, and work collaboratively to solve problems. Such processes support deeper processing of information, which has been confirmed in learning theories to strengthen long-term memory. The social interaction and shared responsibility embedded in cooperative learning instructional strategy also promote repeated use and reinforcement of learned concepts, thereby improving retention. In contrast, the lecture method, which places students in passive roles with limited opportunities for meaningful engagement, appears less effective in helping students retain Biology content over time. Memory research suggests that information presented in a passive, one-way format is more likely to fade quickly because learners do not actively process the content or connect it to prior knowledge. This may explain the significantly lower delayed post-test scores recorded by students taught through the lecture method. The results align with previous research by Melkamu, Tariku, and Wudu (2024), Aisha, Jamilu, and Salisu (2023), and Ndukwe, Ugama, Ikporo, and Ngwu (2021), who in their different studies found a noteworthy variation in students' retention capacity, favouring the group that received instruction using cooperative learning instructional strategy.

The fourth finding of this study from Tables 7 and 8 indicated that the cooperative learning instructional strategy is more effective in improving students' attitudes toward biology than the traditional lecture method. Cooperative learning promotes active engagement, social interaction, peer support, and a sense of belonging—all of which can significantly influence learners' motivation and disposition toward a subject. Through teamwork, shared responsibility, and positive interdependence, students are likely to develop greater interest, enjoyment, and confidence in learning biology concepts. On the other hand, the lower attitude scores among students taught with the lecture method may be attributed to the passive nature of the approach. Lecture-based instruction often limits students' participation, discourages questioning, and provides fewer opportunities for hands-on or collaborative activities, which can negatively affect learners' intrinsic motivation and attitude toward the subject. The findings align with several empirical studies, such as those of Odutuyi (2024), Oni (2021), Syeda, Muhammad, Habiba, Um-e-Farwa, and Abida (2022), and Alhassan (2019), who reported that cooperative learning enhances students' attitudes toward science subjects by promoting a supportive and inclusive learning atmosphere. Furthermore, the result supports social constructivist principles, which emphasize that learning is strengthened when students interact, share ideas, and build knowledge collaboratively. These interactions not only deepen understanding but also make learning more enjoyable—resulting in more positive attitudes.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings, the study concluded that cooperative learning instructional strategy is more effective in enhancing biology students' achievement, retention, and attitude than the lecture method. Furthermore, the cooperative learning instructional strategy is not gender-biased regarding enhancing biology students' achievement.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Arising from the findings, the study recommended that biology teachers should adopt cooperative learning strategy in their classroom instruction. This approach should be encouraged as it actively engages students in collaborative learning, leading to improved understanding and long-term retention of concepts. Also, cooperative learning is equally effective for both male and female students. Also, the government and educational administrators should organize seminars and workshops through the Ministry of Education to train teachers on how to effectively utilize cooperative learning instructional strategy to teach, as well as furnish schools with relevant educational resources to facilitate the implementation.

REFERENCES

- Ademola, O. O., & Nadaraj, G. (2018). Effectiveness of polya problem-solving and target-task collaborative learning approaches in electricity amongst high school physics students. *Journal of Baltic Science Education*, 17(5), 765-777
- Ahmed, U & Shaista, M. (2016). Secondary school students' attitude towards the social science studies in Sargodha City, Pakistan. *International Journal of Academic Research in Progressive Education and Development*, 5(2), 67-76.
- Ajaja, O. P. (2013). Which strategy best suits biology teaching? Lecturing, concept mapping, cooperative learning, or learning cycle? *Electronic Journal of Science Education*, 17(1), 2-36
- Ajaja, O. P. (2009). *Teaching methods across discipline*. Ibadan, Bomn Prints.
- Chinwe N. & Gloria C. (2014). *Biology laboratory material resource utilization in Colleges of Education: Implication for Biology curriculum delivery in Nigerian Secondary Schools*. Department of science Education, University of Nigeria Nsukka.
- Dan-Olege, I.A. & Shitu A.O. (2012). Improving the standard of teaching and learning of practical in our secondary schools: Emphasis on biology and chemistry practical. *Journal of Qualitative Education*. 8. (1), 1-5.
- Effiom, W. A. & Abdullahi, A. (2021). Effect of polya's problem-solving strategy on senior secondary school students' performance in algebraic word problem in Katsina Metropolis, Katsina State, Nigeria. *Sapientia Foundation Journal of Education, Sciences and Gender Studies* 3(2), 344 – 351.
- Ekinfe, E., Olofinniyi O.E., Fashikun, E.O., (2012). Teachers' quality as correlates of students' academic performance in biology in senior secondary schools in Ondo state, Nigeria. *Journal of Education and research*, 1(1), 108-114.
- Ezeudu, F. O. (2017). Influence of concept maps on achievement retention of senior secondary school students in organic chemistry, *Journal of Education and Practice*, 4(19), 35-44.
- George, R. (2006). A cross-domain analysis of change in students' attitude toward science and attitude about the utility of science. *International Journal of Science Education*, 28, 283-289
- Johnson, D. W & Johnson, R. T. (2009). Oral interaction in co-operative learning group: speaking, listening and the nature of statements made by high- medium- and low achieving students. *Journal of Psychology*, 319,303-321.
- Johnson, D. W., & Johnson, R. T. (2011). Cooperative learning: The encyclopedia of peace psychology.
- Johnson, D.W., Johnson, R.T., & Smith, K. (2013), Cooperative learning: Improving university instruction by basing practice on validated theory. University of Minnesota. *Journal of Excellence in University Teaching*. 1-2
- Ksheerasagar S., & Kavyakishore, P. B. (2013). Achievement in Science of Secondary School Students in Relation to Scientific Attitude. *International Journal of Education and Psychological Research*.2(2), 61 -65.
- Nwagbo, C. R. (2006). Effects of two teaching methods on the achievement and attitude of biology students of different levels of scientific literacy. *International Journal of Education Research*, 45, 216-229
- Nwosu, C.M. (2013). *The impact of cooperative instructional strategy on the performance of grade 09 learners in science*. University of South Africa. 1-98.
- Nwanze, A. C. (2016). Effects of multimedia synchronized instructional strategy on students' achievement and retention in secondary school chemistry in Onitcha education zone. Unpublished M.Ed Dissertation. Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka.
- Olanipekun, S., & Aina, J.K. (2014). Improving students' performance in Nigerian schools: The role of teachers. *International journal of Research in Humanities and Social Studies*, 1, 1-6.
- Osualale, O.J. (2014). Problems of teaching and learning science in junior secondary schools in Nassarawa state, Nigeria. *Journal of Education and Practice*. Vol. 5 (34), 109.

- Salau, M. O. (2009). Effects of class size on achievement of different ability groups in mathematics. *Journal of Science Teachers' Association of Nigeria*, 31(1), 27-33.
- Salihu, Z. (2015). Effects of guided discovery approach on students' academic Performance in ecology in senior secondary schools in Sokoto state Nigeria. *Usman Danfodio University Sokoto*. 1-61.
- Slavin, R.E. (2011). *Instructional based cooperative learning*. John Hopkins University and University of York. 344.
- Umar, B. K., Ossom, M. O., & Egbita, A. U. (2020). Impact of multimedia instructional strategies on students' achievement and retention in basic science and technology in Minna, Niger State. *International Journal of Research and Scientific Innovation* 7(6), 150-155.
- Umar, A. A., Soladoye, L., & Benjamin, B. A. (2022). Attaining meaningful learning of ecological concept: A test of the efficacy of 7E learning cycle model. *International Journal of Educational Research*, 5(4), 18-29